

Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) with Chelating Hydrazones

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Twelve complex compounds having the composition $[ML_2B_2]$, $[ML'_2B_2]$, $[M'L'_2]$ $[M'L'_2]$ have been prepared where $M = Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$, $Cu(II)$; $M' = Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$; LH and $L'H$ are the hydrazones derived from benzoin with phenylhydrazine and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, respectively and $B = H_2O$. As inferred from analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR and electronic spectral data the $Co(II)$ and $Ni(II)$ complexes in the first and second categories are octahedral in configuration, $Cu(II)$ complexes distorted-octahedral and the latter two types of complexes are tetrahedral.

LITERATURE shows that various hydrazones possess strong bactericidal, herbicidal, insecticidal and fungicidal properties¹⁻⁴. Katyal and Dutta⁵ studied the analytical application of hydrazones. A few hydrazones have also been used for the detection and determination of metal ions gravimetrically⁶⁻⁷. Keeping these in view, we have studied some metal complexes with chelating bidentate phenyl/2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones of benzoin, a β -hydroxyketone, and the findings are reported here.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of the ligands: Phenylhydrazine (1.08 g) or 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (1.98 g) in glacial acetic acid was added to ethanolic solution of benzoin (2.12 g) and refluxed for 0.5-1 hr. On keeping overnight, yellow compounds of the corresponding hydrazone separated out which were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried on exposure to air.

Preparation of the complexes: Ethanolic solutions of the metal chlorides were mixed with ethanol solutions of the ligands in 1:2 molar proportion and the resulting solution refluxed for 1 hr. On cooling overnight, crystalline compounds separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metals were estimated by EDTA titration method and nitrogen by microanalysis. The conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using a Toshniwal conductance meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on the solids by the Gouy method. IR spectra were recorded with KBr discs using Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra was recorded in $10^{-3}M$ chloroform solution with a Hilgerwatt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		$\Delta\chi$ mhos cm ³	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\frac{\nu(C=N)}{\nu(C-O)}$
	Metal	Nitrogen			
LH	—	9.27 (9.30)	—	—	1600/1210
L'H	—	14.28 (14.32)	—	—	1615/1210
$[CoL_2B_2]$	8.38 (8.45)	6.35 (6.38)	10.5	5.0	1590/1200
$[CoL'_2B_2]$	6.68 (6.71)	12.64 (12.77)	12.0	4.9	1605/1200
$[NiL_2B_2]$	8.40 (8.42)	6.34 (6.38)	14.5	3.1	1585/1205
$[NiL'_2B_2]$	6.59 (6.69)	12.68 (12.77)	9.7	3.0	1610/1200
$[CuL_2B_2]$	9.0 (9.07)	7.94 (8.00)	8.0	1.78	1590/1200
$[CuL'_2B_2]$	7.19 (7.22)	12.71 (12.73)	9.5	1.75	1605/1200
$[ZnL_2]$	9.75 (9.82)	8.39 (8.41)	8.7	—	1590/1195
$[ZnL'_2]$	7.68 (7.73)	12.21 (13.24)	10.0	—	1600/1200
$[CdL_2]$	15.68 (15.77)	7.82 (7.86)	7.5	—	1585/1200
$[CdL'_2]$	15.53 (15.59)	12.47 (12.55)	7.0	—	1600/1200
$[HgL_2]$	25.0 (25.05)	6.88 (6.99)	10.4	—	1590/1200
$[HgL'_2]$	20.37 (20.45)	11.38 (11.42)	12.5	—	1605/1200

LH and L'H = Hydrazones derived from benzoin with phenylhydrazine and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The complexes isolated are of the types $[ML_2B_2]$, $[ML'_2B_2]$, $[M'L_2]$ and $[M'L'_2]$ where $M = Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$ or $Cu(II)$; $M' = Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$ or $Hg(II)$; LH and $L'H$ = hydrazones derived from benzoin with phenyl hydrazine and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, respectively and $B = H_2O$.

Cobalt complexes are pink, nickel complexes green, copper complexes blue, zinc complexes yellowish white to white, cadmium complexes white and the two mercury complexes are yellow to greyish-white, in colour. All the complexes have low molar conductances in acetone medium indicating non-electrolytic nature. The magnetic moment values show the presence of three, two and one unpaired electrons in cases of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes, respectively.

The ir spectra of the ligands and the metal chelates are quite illustrative. The ligand molecules possess two potential donor sites namely, the hydroxylic oxygen and the hydrazine nitrogen atoms. In the ligands $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ appeared at 1600 cm^{-1} in the case of phenylhydrazone and at 1615 cm^{-1} in the case of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. In the metal complexes a decrease of $10\text{-}15\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the bonding of hydrazinic nitrogen atom to the metal ions. The appearance of the band at 1210 cm^{-1} in the ligands can be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibration. This band has been shifted down to lower frequencies of $\sim 1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the chelates showing the coordination of hydroxylic oxygen atom to metal ions. The ligands as well as metal chelates have two absorption bands in $\sim 3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region assignable to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and in the $1500\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region assignable to $\sigma(\text{NH})$ vibration, which shows the non-coordination of secondary amino group with metal ions. In the cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes the presence of coordinated water is confirmed^{8,9} by the observation of a broad double-hump around 3450 cm^{-1} . However, the conclusive evidence of the bonding of oxygen and nitrogen atoms has been provided¹⁰ by the occurrence of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ at $\sim 450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions, respectively in the complexes.

In the visible electronic spectrum of the nickel(II) complexes, three bands were observed at 8500 (7.5) , 18500 (9.5) and $25000\text{ (18.5)}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions, respectively. Low molar extinction coefficients and characteristic magnetic moments support a spin-free octahedral structure of these

complexes. In case of the cobalt(II) complexes, absorption bands appear at 8000 (15) and 20500 (19) , assignable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions, respectively. Three transitions are expected for cobalt(II) complexes of Oh symmetry. The ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ transition involving a two-electron process gives rise to a weak band on the high frequency side of the ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ band. The low intensity combined with closeness to the ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition makes its detection in the present case difficult. The two copper(II) complexes show an electronic spectral band in the region $13500\text{-}16000$ which may be assigned to the transition $2\text{E}_g \rightarrow 2\text{T}_{2g}$ characteristic of distorted-octahedral copper(II) complexes¹¹.

The Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are presumably tetrahedral in configuration on the basis of analysis, conductance and ir spectral data.

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